

DESIRABLE ASPECTS OF VISUAL PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES FOR DIFFERENT APPLICATIONS IN MUSIC CREATION

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ABSTRACT

Visual programming languages are commonly used in the domain of sound and music creation. Specific properties and paradigms of those visual languages make them convenient and appealing to artists in various applications such as computer composition, sound synthesis, multimedia artworks, and development of interactive system. This paper presents a systematic research of several well-known languages for sound and music creation. The research was based on the analysis of cognitive dimensions such as abstraction gradient, consistency, closeness of mapping, and error-proneness. We have also considered the context of each analyzed language including its availability, community, and learning materials. Data for the research were collected from a survey conducted among users of the most notable and widespread visual programming languages. The data is presented both in raw, textual format and in a summarized table view. The results indicate desirable aspects along with possible improvements of visual programming approaches for different use cases. Finally, future research directions and goals are suggested in the field of visual programming for applications in music.

1. INTRODUCTION

The usefulness of visual programming for various domains has been researched extensively as well as the motives and reasons which typically drive users to adopt and adapt to visual programming [1]. Research shows that visual paradigms are better suited for novice users and are easier to understand for non-expert users in general. The most often cited reasons for this are the inherent predisposition of the human psychology towards visual, instead of textual representations and the inclusion of domain specific, immediately understandable syntactic elements such as musical instruments [2]. However, the specific links between artists, in this case musicians, and visual programming has not been explored extensively. We think that this is something worth researching as the field itself is interesting and unique, a touching point between arts and engineering, and the visual approach seems to be quite fruitful and well adopted in the field [3]. Languages and tools for computer composition, music creation, and sound synthesis are predominantly of the

visual kind and it has been shown that musicians avoid conventional textual languages [4].

The aim and purpose of this paper is to better understand why musicians find visual programming so appealing, which aspects of existing languages they find most useful and for which applications, and what problems do they encounter while using them. Primarily, we wanted to identify why certain languages seem well-suited for specific applications in music, from sound synthesis to algorithmic composition. In a way, this work can be seen as the first step on the journey of trying to understand how and why certain paradigms and approaches inspire artists when dealing with computer created music. The impact of tool choices on creativity is also briefly considered. Additionally, in this paper we present a succinct cross-examination and comparison of selected languages and tools based on their design choices.

Since neither hard data nor related research existed that would help us determine which specific properties and aspects of visual programming users find appealing, we conducted a survey among the users of the selected five most significant languages. The user base we surveyed was predominantly comprised of amateur musicians. The collected data and extrapolated knowledge presented in this paper has been judged, internally, against the cognitive dimensions framework [1]. We used the framework to try and identify key concepts of these languages and we employed its principles to help us deduce the positives and negatives of each aspect of visual programming languages. Detailed analysis based on the cognitive framework is beyond the scope of this paper.

The rest of this paper is divided as follows: the second chapter gives a basic overview of the programming languages and tools that we included in our research. The third chapter discusses the methodology used to collect the data and gives insights into the users' responses. In the fourth chapter we try to identify what and why users value in programming languages for music creation. In closing, we propose topics for future research.

2. VISUAL PROGRAMMING AND MUSIC

As stated previously, visual programming is often used in computer-supported music creation processes. From synthesizing basic sounds to algorithmic composition and complex audiovisual works, the number and type of applications are practically limitless. For our questionnaire we selected five languages and tools that cover all of

these purposes, but during the selection process we also considered their reach and influence. The final selection was reduced to the following five languages and tools: Pure Data, Max/MSP, OpenMusic, Symbolic Sound Kyma, and Native Instruments Reaktor.

Figure 1. Pure Data, Max/MSP [5], and OpenMusic

In the following text as well as in the surveys, we used nomenclature tied to each of the individual languages. In other words, terms like “class”, “object”, and “sound” may refer to very similar concepts in the context of Pure Data, OpenMusic, or Kyma respectively. We decided that this approach would help minimize any misunderstandings and uncertainties that would have been introduced by a generalized, common codification.

2.1 Pure Data

Pure Data [6] is an open source visual programming language geared towards sound processing and generation, music creation, and artistic multimedia work in general.

On a paradigm level, Pure Data is a dataflow programming language. The flow consists either of control messages or audio signals which are processed by native objects providing functionalities ranging from simpler (mathematical operations and general programming functionalities) to complex digital signal processing. The feature set available through native objects and extensions called “externals” is very wide making Pure Data usable not only as a language for creating sounds, videos,

and other multimedia, but to create fully fledged programs.

This flexibility is twofold. On one side, it is powerful and enables its users to make anything they want, but on the other side it requires a better knowledge and understanding of programming on a lower level. This is especially clear when taking into consideration the signal flow it is based on. Further positives include the variety of available patches and the possibility of interfacing with various other hardware and software tools, libraries, and systems making it suitable for creating interactive systems. Among other negatives, a certain lack of visual polish stands out as well as rudimentary support for higher level functionalities and out of the box functionalities.

2.2 Max/MSP

Max/MSP is a language that is superficially fairly similar to Pure Data since they stem from the same author. Max/MSP and Pure Data fall under the moniker of “patcher” languages [7], and they both share significant features and use cases, while portions of their code can even be interoperated and used with either of the programming languages. One important benefit of Max/MSP is a user interface with many usability improvements, better organization of components, and the availability of additional tools such as tags and searches which improves programming efficiency. The graphical design with customizable elements contributes to better intelligibility and overall impression of the workspace. Some objects have a rich visual representation which illustrates nicely the purpose of the object and sometimes even allow interactivity over its parameters. Since Max/MSP is nowadays a proprietary and commercial product [5], the user base is somewhat smaller, but the users in turn benefit from improvements not available in Pure Data.

2.3 OpenMusic

In basic terms, OpenMusic [8][9] is an object-oriented visual programming language. While it possesses a number of functionalities that make it usable as a general purpose language, Open Music is a tool heavily adapted for algorithmic composition and automation of composition techniques. Standout features include objects that resemble the traditional musical notation as well as a variety of objects that diverge from the underlying signal flow paradigm and enable the manipulation of sounds in time. Being based on Lisp, it retains many of its characteristics.

While not as flexible nor extensible as Pure Data or Max/MSP, it provides many additional features that might make it easier to use when dealing purely with music composition. Users well-versed in Lisp might also find OpenMusic appealing because of the modifications made available through core changes.

2.4 Symbolic Sound Kyma

Kyma, a “sound design” graphic language, is geared primarily towards live, interactive sound generation and manipulation, and post-production [10]. Being concentrated mainly on the manipulation of sounds and disre-

garding other elements of multimedia, it is primarily suited for music composition and a variety of music manipulation techniques.

The paradigm includes many aspects and additional tools that are not available in competing products making it easier to use, more streamlined, and less error prone. Especially notable is the timeline that enables the manipulation of sounds in the domain of time, similar to those found in digital audio workstation software.

Its reach and acceptance were influenced, since the very beginning, by the cost of ownership and mandatory hardware associated with the software. Because of those factors, Kyma has been and, to a lesser degree, still is used mainly in the Academia.

Figure 2. Symbolic Sound Kyma [11] and Native Instruments Reaktor [12]

2.5 Native Instruments Reaktor

Reaktor is a modular studio for designing sound synthesizers, sequencers, samplers, audio effects, and other sound design tools. Unlike all previously mentioned tools and languages, Reaktor is not intended for creating music compositions, interactive systems, or multimedia works. It is focused on developing objects for sound synthesis and processing which then can be combined and superimposed. Additionally to objects created using the visual paradigm on several different abstraction levels, Reaktor also provides the possibility to view and edit building blocks using textual programming. Sound synthesizers and effects developed in Reaktor can be used within host sequencers and digital audio workstations. This kind of a toolset clearly suits a different target audience when compared to the other described languages.

3. RESEARCH AND FINDINGS

In this chapter, after first explaining the methodology used in our research, we present the survey results that point towards some interesting aspects and tendencies regarding the selected languages. Further analysis and conclusions are laid out in the subsequent chapter.

3.1 Methodology

The data presented in this paper was collected in four phases. During the first phase, we created questionnaires for the selected visual programming languages and tools based on existing research and our own previous analysis. The questions were modeled so that they would provide us with knowledge about certain interesting aspects of these languages and their impact on users.

To improve the questionnaires, during the second phase we conducted interviews with experienced users for each of the selected programming languages. The collected data helped us to ensure the correct terminology, intelligibility of questions, and relevance of the answers offered for closed-type questions.

The third phase included posting the questionnaires on a variety of appropriate community web pages, forums, and social networks to be filled by users. The questionnaires were available for one week for collecting answers.

The fourth and final phase consisted of data analysis. For this purpose, we used IBM's SPSS Statistics software package [13]. Each questionnaire was processed individually and no cross-analysis was performed between the sets of data. The output of the software package has been manually corrected for certain outliers.

Also worth noting is that the questions in the questionnaires were divided into two sets. The first set of questions included common questions that were the same for each of the languages. These dealt with demographic data, how the users became accustomed with the specific language, inquiries about other tools that they might have used, etc. On the other hand, the second set was comprised of questions tailored around the specificities of individual languages. For example, the questionnaire for Native Instruments' Reaktor did not include questions about algorithmic composition since it cannot support such constructs.

3.2 Pure Data

There were 56 participants who answered questions about Pure Data, 91% male, aged between 17 and 59 ($M=31.37$, $SD=9.64$), with 68% having a formal music education. They found out about Pure Data from a friend or colleague (48%), during university (19%), from a magazine, journal, or a book (14%), and online (14%). They have been using it for more than 2 years (55%), between 1 and 2 years (20%), between 3 months and a year (16%), and less than 3 months (9%). They have been using it every day (18%), few times a week (36%), few times per month (34%), and few times per year (12%). They have made between 0 and 100 works ($M=14.49$, $SD=17.52$). Most of them said that it took a few weeks (34%) or a few months (34%) to become productive, for 14% it took a few days and for 18% a year or more. They use Pure Data mostly

for creating interactive systems (70%), musical compositions (68%), and audio effects (66%), automating composition techniques (46%), creating synthesizers that are subsequently used in compositions (43%), and audiovisual works (38%). Participants use Pure Data to create algorithmic compositions (63%), laptop improvisations (59%), acousmatic music (41%), and accompaniments for acoustic instruments or ensembles (36%). They chose Pure Data because, in comparison to other languages/tools, it is better for their needs (38%), they understand it better (34%), it is simpler to use (20%), or because it is free (14%). They have learned how to use it from online tutorials (82%), from a book (34%), during a university course (16%), or with a help of colleague (16%). Learning became easier or easy after they learned the basics (88%). Most of them are satisfied or somewhat satisfied with the visibility and legibility of their programs (61%) and think that other users would significantly or completely understand their programs (59%). They think the most inspiring aspect of Pure Data are the flexibility of the language (support for various usages) (46%), the community and support provided (21%) and cross-platform support (16%). They think there is a subtle (39%) or moderate (38%) difference between their personal way of thinking and the concepts used in Pure Data, and they think what is missing in Pure Data is a temporal dimension (39%), visualization of a timbral characteristics and changes in sound (39%) and visualization of sound spatialization (34%). The most tedious aspect for 34% is program flow control, for 23% synchronization of events in time, for 20% mapping and scaling numerical values and for 16% analysis, synthesis, and processing of audio signals. There was no consensus on limitations. Most of Pure Data users (61%) are also acquainted with Max/MSP, 27% also know NI Reaktor, while 25% know only Pure Data.

When programming in Pure Data, participants have controls and some other pieces of the patch opened in the main patch (39%) or only controls (30%). 71% of them use example patches or other people's patches and 61% annotate them sometimes or often, with 36% saying they use comments for annotations. Most of them think they make mistakes sometimes (55%), that it is moderately difficult to notice errors and mistakes (55%), and that it is moderately difficult to understand roles of certain portions of program (66%). Also, most of them think they have to rearrange elements often or always (70%), and that it is easy or moderately difficult to modify existing programs (71%). For 55% of participants, components sometimes behave in unwanted ways, they test unfinished patches often or always (74%), and find this a useful or very useful possibility (93%). 48% of them think that the debugging tool's limitations hinders the evaluation of unfinished programs, while 39% think that there is a need for temporarily placed connectors and objects.

3.3 Max/MSP

There were 18 participants who answered questions about Max/MSP, they were all male, aged between 22 and 57 ($M=33.44$, $SD=9.67$), and 60% had formal music education. They found out about Max/MSP from a magazine,

journal or a book (28%), during university (28%), online (22%), from a friend or colleague (17%), and during conferences (5%). They have been using it for more than 2 years (67%), between 1 and 2 years (22%), and less than a year (11%). They have been using it every day (44%), few times a week (17%), and few times per month (33%). Only one participant stated that he uses it few times per year. They have made between 0 and 200 works ($M=24.56$, $SD=46.39$). Most of them said that it took a few weeks to become productive (39%), for 33% it took a few months, for 17% a few days, and for 11% a year or more. They use Max/MSP mostly for creating musical compositions (78%), creating audio effects and automating composition techniques (50%), creating interactive systems (44%), audiovisual works (39%), and synthesizers later used in compositions (33%). Participants make algorithmic compositions (67%), laptop improvisations (44%), acousmatic music (28%), and accompaniment for an acoustic instrument or ensemble (11%). They chose Max/MSP because they understand it better than other languages (61%), it is better for their needs (44%) or it is simpler to use (28%). They have learned how to use it with online tutorials (61%) and during a university course (39%), and learning became easier or easy after they learned the basics (94%). 33% of them are satisfied with using Max/MSP, 44% somewhat satisfied, and 22% somewhat unsatisfied. Most of them think that other users would somewhat understand their programs (50%), with additional 39% thinking that other users would understand them significantly or completely. They think the most inspiring aspect of Max/MSP is the flexibility of the language (support for various usages). The most important limitation for 50% is the lack of explicit temporal dimension and for 44% the lack of appropriate tools for exporting MIDI/sheet music. In line with that, 44% say what is missing in Max/MSP is a temporal dimension, 33% say visualization of a timbral characteristics and changes in sound, and 22% visualization of sound spatialization. The most tedious aspect for 39% is synchronization of events in time, for 22% program flow control, and for 17% analysis, synthesis, and processing of audio signals. Most of them (44%) know only Max/MSP, 39% know also Pure Data and 28% know also NI Reaktor.

Participants differed in how they would describe the difference between their visual representation and the one used in Max/MSP: 16% think there is no difference, 28% think there is a subtle, 28% there is a moderate, and 28% there is a significant difference. When working with Max/MSP, most of them (56%) have controls and some other pieces of the patch open in the main patch. 61% of them use example patches or other people's patches and annotate them sometimes or often, with 39% saying they use comments for annotations. Most of them think it is moderately difficult to notice errors and mistakes (72%) and to understand roles of certain portions of program (77%). Also, most of them think that sometimes or often they make mistakes (84%) and have to rearrange elements (77%), and that it is easy or moderately difficult to modify existing programs (77%). For 56% components sometimes behave in unwanted ways, they test unfinished patches often or always (83%) and find this a useful or

very useful possibility (83%). 56% of them think that the debugging tool's limitations hinder the evaluation of unfinished programs, while 33% think that there is a need for temporary connectors and objects.

3.4 OpenMusic

Due to the limited number of responses to this questionnaire, the data presented for OpenMusic is statistically unreliable, but it nonetheless helps better understand some aspects of the language.

There were 3 participants who answered questions about OpenMusic, they were all male, aged between 24 and 51, and all had high levels of formal music education. They found out about OpenMusic during university (67%) and from a friend or colleague (33%). They have been using it from more than 3 months to more than 2 years. They use it from few times per month to everyday. They have made between 1 and 20 works. It took a few weeks for them to become productive. They use OpenMusic for creating musical compositions (acousmatic music and algorithmic compositions) and automating composition techniques. They chose OpenMusic because it is simpler to use and better suited for their needs. They have learned how to use it by consulting written online tutorials and books, and they find that learning became easier after becoming acquainted with the basics. They have different opinions about whether other users would understand their programs, ranging from not at all to completely. Each participant named different limitations of OpenMusic and all of them have different ideas about what is missing from OpenMusic's visual representation, but two of them think that most tedious aspect is the reliance on program flow control. Two of them also think that the most inspiring aspect are visual representations which include sheet music. They all also know Max/MSP, two of them also know Pure Data, and one also knows NI Reaktor.

As mentioned before, the number of respondents was small, so we will only report what the respondents agreed on when discussing the process of working in OpenMusic. They think it is easy or moderately difficult to notice errors and mistakes, that it is moderately difficult to modify existing programs, and that it is useful or very useful that they can evaluate unfinished programs, with debugging tool's limitations hindering the evaluation of unfinished programs the most. In their opinion, programs sometimes behave in unwanted ways and they find it moderately difficult or difficult to understand the roles of certain portions of the program. They are somewhat satisfied with OpenMusic, they often use existing functions, and always use existing classes. They find the possibility to choose icons useful, but that the purpose of existing classes is somewhat unclear from their icons.

3.5 Symbolic Sound Kyma

Similar to OpenMusic, we received a limited number of responses to the questionnaire for Kyma. While it remains statistically unreliable, our confidence in the collected data is higher due to interviews conducted with users who are Kyma experts, highly educated, and have

been using the system for many years (more than 10, in some cases).

There were 5 participants who answered questions about Kyma, they were all male, aged between 39 and 61 ($M=44.60$, $SD=9.24$), and 60% had formal music education. They found out about Kyma from a magazine, journal, book or radio program (40%), during university courses (40%), and during research (20%). They have been using it either more than 2 years (80%) or between 1 and 2 years (20%). They mostly use it a few times per year (80%) and only one participant stated that he uses it every day. They have made between 3 and 300 works ($M=69.20$, $SD=129.35$). It took a few weeks to become productive for 40%, a year or more for 40%, and a few days for 20% of the participants. They use Kyma mostly for creating musical compositions (100%), making synthesizers that are subsequently used in compositions (60%), audio effects (40%), and interactive systems (40%). Participants mostly make acousmatic music (60%) and accompaniment for acoustic instruments or ensembles (60%). They chose Kyma because it is better suited for their needs (60%). They have learned how to use it mostly from a book (80%) and learning became easier or easy after they learned the basics (60%); 40% of them find that other users would completely understand their programs. Each participant named different inspiring aspects and limitations of Kyma, but 40% named parameter automation, 40% the possibility of creating new from existing objects, and 20% mentioned the large number of existing sounds as the most useful aspect of Kyma. 40% of the respondents are also acquainted with NI Reaktor and 40% with Max/MSP.

Kyma users often use existing sounds (60%) and tools (60%), while they never or rarely use colors to annotate sounds (80%). 60% say it is easy to find the right module, 80% say they do not have problems finding the right module, and 60% say that do not have problems with the unavailability of required modules. Regarding errors, 40% say they never make them, 40% that they sometimes make them, 40% think errors and mistakes are very difficult to notice, and 40% sometimes rearrange modules. 80% find it easy to modify existing sounds and 80% think it is easy or moderately difficult to understand the roles of existing sounds. As for satisfaction with the visibility and legibility of their sounds, 40% are somewhat unsatisfied and 40% are somewhat satisfied.

3.6 Native Instruments Reaktor

There were 13 participants who answered questions about NI Reaktor. They were all male, aged between 20 and 59 ($M=35.00$, $SD=12.77$), and 54% had no formal music education. They found out about NI Reaktor from a friend or colleague (25%), magazine, journal or a book (25%), online (17%), through another product of the same company (17%), during university courses (8%), or conferences (8%). They have been using it more than 2 years (54%), between 3 months and a year (31%) and between 1 and 2 years (15%). They have been using it every day (38%), a few times a week (31%), and few times per month (23%). Only one participant stated that he uses it a few times per year. They have made between

3 and 352 works ($M=56.46$, $SD=102.86$). Most of them said that it took a few months to become productive (62%), for 23% it took a few weeks, and for 15% a year or more. They use NI Reaktor mostly for creating musical compositions (54%), audio effects (62%) and synthesizers subsequently used in compositions (46%). They chose NI Reaktor because it is simpler to use (23%), they understand it better (15%), or it is better for their needs (15%). They have learned how to use it mostly with online tutorials (77%), and learning became easier or easy after they learned the basics (93%). 62% of them are satisfied with using NI Reaktor and find that other users would significantly or completely understand their programs (85%). They use it because it enables them to create works which cannot be made in other tools (39%) and because of its flexibility and creative possibilities (31%). For 54% the most important limitation is that instruments cannot be compiled to work outside Reaktor (e.g. as VST instruments). Most of them (54%) know only NI Reaktor, and 38% know also Max/MSP.

As much as 77% of users often or always use existing ensembles and instruments, and the rest use them at least sometimes. For existing macros, 46% use them rarely or sometimes and 54% use them often or always. Existing cells are used often or always (77%). On the core level NI Reaktor is used rarely or sometimes (54%), but 39% of participants stated that they never use it on the core level. They also rarely or sometimes use play mode (77%), they think that mistakes and errors are only rarely or sometimes a consequence of mixing events and audio signals (70%), and for them most common mistakes are connecting polyphonic macros or modules to monophonic ones (23%) and normalization and scaling of numeric values (23%). When they create new instruments they sometimes or often (70%) encounter components that are not clear to them, they find it moderately difficult to find the components they need (62%), and 54% think that unclear functionalities of some components complicate the process of finding the right component. For 62% of the respondents, components sometimes behave in unwanted ways, it is moderately difficult to modify existing ensembles and instruments and to understand their purpose, and it is somewhat clear what are the functionalities and roles of components. When they want information about components, they search online tutorials (54%) or read user manuals (31%). When it comes to rearranging components, 31% of the participants rearrange them often, 23% always, and 23% sometimes. 70% of participants sometimes or often group their instruments, rewrite significant portions of their instruments, and make mistakes that require significant changes. 77% find it useful to evaluate unfinished instruments and 46% of them think that the need for temporary connectors and components hinders the evaluation of unfinished instruments, while 31% think it is the debugging tool's limitations. They mostly do not think that the experience of using Reaktor would improve if the flow was vertical rather than horizontal (70%).

3.7 Summary

To improve the readability of some key data, we include a summary, in the form of a table (Table 1), of the most

important questions and answers. This summary improves the comprehension of the following chapter.

4. ANALYSIS, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

Analysis of the collected data (see Table 1 for a summarized view) shows many interesting tendencies and patterns. Particularly, this research has confirmed that the visual nature of these languages removes hurdles between artists and their ideas, enabling them to become productive in a relatively short period.

On a more superficial level, it is clear that most users tend to commit to only one language and only sparsely use or try out alternatives, regardless of the type of task they are trying to accomplish. This is true even in those instances when better, more fitting languages are available. For example, while Kyma is best suited for sound design and OpenMusic is oriented towards algorithmic composition, users insist on using Pure Data for these applications. What is obvious from the results and answers is that Pure Data and Max/MSP users are not aware of commercial tools such as Kyma or of more recent and less widespread tools such as Open Music.

Based on the number of responses as well as other metrics such as the Alexa page rank or number of citations in publications, we can conclude that most users gravitate towards open source languages such as Pure Data which, in turn, has the most diverse and largest user base. The lower cost of tools or the availability of online literature can be reasons for that, but this can also be explained by the "do it yourself" nature of the language, the encompassing culture and community, and the vast range of functionalities provided. While there is no consensus as far as its limitations are concerned, it is obvious that many users resent the somewhat dated look and feel of the language/environment. Many of the issues that they mention, such as the lack of a timeline, have already been resolved in languages that they are not acquainted with (most often Kyma). Respondents point out that the lack of a temporal dimension and the over-reliance on signal flow also hinder productivity, but whether or not this has any bearing on the quality of their output cannot be determined. For many, Pure Data requires additional efforts to tackle and harness, asking for deeper knowledge about programming. The question is raised, in the end, whether these obstacles actually have any impact on creativity since almost all users seem satisfied with Pure Data in general.

Similar judgments can be made about the other languages as well. The survey results have shown that some common preconceptions are, indeed, correct. For example, when considering use cases, Pure Data is predominantly used for interactive systems and music composition, Max/MSP for automated composition techniques, Kyma for music compositions and creating synthesizers, Reaktor for sound effects, etc. Whether it is a question of marketing or truly related to the specifics of each language remains unclear, especially when considering the users' reluctance of trying out other software.

	Pure Data	Max / MPS	Open Music	Kyma	NI Reaktor
Number of participants	56	18	3	5	13
Age	range: 17 to 59 mean: 31.7	range: 22 to 57 mean: 33.4	range: 24 to 51 mean: 36.3	range: 39 to 61 mean: 44.6	range: 20 to 59 mean: 35.0
Experience in using the language	> 2 years: 55% 1-2 years: 20% < 1 year: 25%	> 2 years: 67% 1-2 years: 22% < 1 year: 11%	> 2 years: 2 < 1 year: 1	> 2 years: 80% 1-2 years: 20%	> 2 years: 54% 1-2 years: 15% < 1 year: 31%
Time to become productive	few days: 14% few weeks: 34% few months: 34% > 1 year: 18%	few days: 17% few weeks: 39% few months: 33% > 1 year: 11%	a few weeks	few days: 20% few weeks: 40% > 1 year: 40%	few weeks: 23% few months: 62% > 1 year: 15%
Frequency of usage	few times per: - day: 18% - week: 36% - month: 34% - year: 12%	few times per: - day: 44% - week: 17% - month: 33% - year: 1	from few times per month to everyday	few times per year: 80% every day: 20%	few times per: - day: 38% - week: 31% - month: 23% - year: 1
Purpose of usage	interactive sys., compositions, automation of comp. techniques	compositions, audio effects, automation of comp. techniques	compositions, automation of comp. techniques	compositions, synthesizers	audio effects, compositions, synthesizers
Knowledge of other languages	Max/MSP: 61% Reaktor: 27%	Pure Data: 39% Reaktor: 28%	Max/MPS: 3 Pure Data: 2 Reaktor: 1	Max/MSP: 40% Reaktor: 40%	Max/MSP: 38%
Frequency of making mistakes	never: 2% rarely: 18% sometimes: 55% often: 16% always: 9%	never: 0% rarely: 17% sometimes: 56% often: 28% always: 0%	rarely: 1 sometimes: 1 always: 1	never: 40% rarely: 0% sometimes: 40% often: 0% always: 20%	never: 8% rarely: 0% sometimes: 23% often: 31% always: 38%
Difficulty of noticing mistakes	easy: 11% moderate: 55% difficult: 30% very difficult: 4%	easy: 11% moderate: 72% difficult: 17% very difficult: 0%	easy: 1 moderate: 2	easy: 20% moderate: 20% difficult: 0% very diff.: 40%	N/A
Most tedious aspects	flow control, synchronization of events	synchronization of events, flow control	flow control	N/A	N/A
Most inspiring aspects	flexibility, community	flexibility	visual representation of sheet music	parameter automation, reuse of objects	N/A

Table 1. Important results obtained by the survey.

Additionally, while most users across the various visual programming languages share the same education and experience levels, the most startling discrepancies are found within Native Instruments Reaktor’s user base. In general, they show a lack of formal education, they are even more heavily exclusive to Reaktor than is the general case, and they tend to shy away from using Reaktor’s advanced functionalities such as editing the fundamental building blocks with textual programming.

Bearing that in mind, it is not surprising that users usually pick out the most apparent features of each language as those that most inspire them. Max and Pure Data experts note their flexibility, Kyma’s user base insists on the potentials of its sound design tools (for example, parameter automatization and the spectrum editor), while OpenMusic users value its sheet input and maquette. We can ascertain that most tools have adapted to the needs of their users.

It appears that most musicians and artists do not think that any radical paradigm shifts are necessary when con-

sidering the tools that they use. Still, it is worth noting that many languages are evolving to include a variety of additional tools whilst the main, basic paradigm stays the same. One notable example is the timeline functionality that was added to Kyma in its later years. Refinements and improvements of existing mechanisms are sought out constantly. Another path worth exploring are specific tools that aid the main functionalities of programming languages such as the spectral editor in Kyma or the simple importer of multimedia files in Max/MSP. The questionnaire results confirmed the intuition that such specific tools are considered to be useful in practical and frequent tasks. Regarding other visual programming aspects, Kyma’s resistance to errors, which stems from an inherent quality of its paradigm and makes it most suitable for inexperienced users approaching sound design, is one example of such improvements.

As far as problems with the languages are concerned, most of them are inherent to the visual domain [1]. Other than that, the lack of program control flow in Kyma and

Reaktor is identified as a problem by some of their users. While it seems that most of the described languages are relatively easy to start working with, more difficult tasks and complex works require a certain amount of experience. There are some further issues prompted by the users which are common to almost all of the analyzed languages. For example: the synchronization of events in time, the underlying signal flow, and the lack of temporal dimensions. Inevitably, some of these issues cannot be resolved without a paradigm shift. Because of that, we believe that new approaches and paradigms could be beneficial to artists' outputs if they offered attractive advantages and solved enough important problems to make them try something new. One such approach could include using a flow based on timbral attributes instead of a conventional signal flow [14].

In conclusion, several interesting points for future work are revealed. First of all, a deeper and more detailed cross-analysis of these languages based on the cognitive dimensions framework must be considered. This kind of broader inquiries could help pinpoint exact areas that could be improved as well as it could shine light on the means of improving them. Questions of creativity left unanswered by this paper should also become clearer. Secondly, and drawing from the first point, worth considering is research into paradigms that would take into account the historic and current developments in the field, but which would also try to fundamentally challenge and change some basic principles. Finally, issues related to gender inequality in the field (shown by our demographic data) and social and subcultural concerns, which might be tangentially related to questions of creativity, should be explored by researchers from appropriate fields.

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